

The background of the entire page is a stylized illustration of pomegranate branches. The branches are dark brown and curve across the frame. They are covered with small, light green leaves and several large, ripe pomegranates in shades of magenta and red. Some pomegranates are fully open, showing their seeds, while others are still closed. The overall style is reminiscent of traditional folk art or a woodcut print.

Visual Notes
from the

XXI INQUA

International Union for
Quaternary Research

roma
2023

Illustrated and Designed by

Captured in situ by Ian Cooke-Tapia during the INQUA 2023 conference

Illustrations by Perizat Karzhau working for Cooked Illustrations

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Lack of knowledge creates disasters.

I am no stranger to scientific conferences.

I have vague memories of attending them when I was very young, and a very particular memory of running around the garden of the Tupper Building of the Smithsonian Tropical Research Institute in Panama during a poster session while my father talked shop and enjoyed a beer.

What was novel this time around was to be on the other side, holding the microphone and presenting my work to an audience of experts in their particular fields. A novel experience for both sides, I hope, for when your expertise is in communicating complex ideas creatively, you have to do it with gusto and flair.

I'd like to say that it was a successful first credit at a conference.

The campus of Sapienza Università sang with cicadas. People gathered by the nasoni fountains bringing cold water, refilling bottles and splashing their faces. A historic heatwave making some of the conference themes of climate change and human impacts all the more real.

INQUA Rome was a sweltering, beautiful gathering of the International Union for Quaternary Research, an organisation founded in 1928 by scientists to improve the understanding of environmental changes and processes during the glacial ages, using interdisciplinary approaches. And that diversity of research and thought was apparent at a glance at both the extensive and rich programme and the make up of the crowds attending. This might be my newbie side speaking, but I have, frankly, never seen researchers from what felt like a truly global perspective in one place.

The study of the past, to better understand the complex processes of this beautiful planet during the last 2.58 million years, seems to have reached us on that hot week. Themes of the colonised landscape, new mathematical models providing stronger evidence for theories, data that is foundational to conservation of existing landscapes, and multidisciplinary approaches.

As a layperson, as an artist fascinated by these subjects, it was enlightening to hear these talks. How could I have ever realised that the bacterial composition of soils is supremely important to certain archaeological contexts? Or that fish-hook technology can be used as a proxy for human migration? Even the intricacies of ice cores, however boring that particular talk was, seemed to have a sudden importance that I could have never seen myself.

The thing is that, now that I write this, I wonder how can we make the excitement for this science spread further. I do not believe these themes are impenetrable, rather I believe they are important for as many people to understand. Complexity of the world is a form of aesthetic beauty to me, something to strive for. Because it gives you this moment of absolute beauty in complexity.

I hope that this document does a little to bring these wonderful ideas, these ideas that help us see the beautiful complexity of the world, to a wider audience. As a science communicator acting as witness during the event, this summary of the conference is an editorialised snippet of the whole. If you're reading this, I ask you that you share it with those you think will find it interesting, useful, and beautiful.

Ian Cooke Tapia
Caerdydd
October, 2023

Scientists

P Ramya Bala

talked about

“What humans find valuable may have huge ecological effects. It may completely define how we manage, treat and relate to land.”

In the historical context of the **State of Tamil Nadu** in Southern India, there is a long history of land management redefining what a “**natural system**” looks like along cultural lines. This presents conservationists with specific questions and issues to resolve. Just in the

recent past, the landscape has shifted several times: from traditional grassland grazing of the Toda buffalo managed by the Toda people, to hunting grounds and grasslands used by the British administration, to mass forestry and industrial plantations most recently.

Maintained grasslands for Toda buffalo by the Toda People.

The grasslands are maintained for hunting due to British sentiment.

Grasslands replaced by forest plantations for fuel and industry.

Modern conservation of Grasslands and the Nilgiri Rhododendron.

Without evidence-based understanding of the past, it is difficult to know what the natural system is.

Modern ecological experiments and ecological information from the past are necessary to develop a deeper understanding of the changing landscape to inform **conservation policies** for the **present and the future**.

Kenta Sayama

talked about

What is a Geoheritage site?

“Features of geology that are intrinsically important or culturally important that offer information and insights into the formation of Earth, the history of science, or that can be used for education, research and reference.”

However, historically, **70% of evaluation methodologies** for geoheritage sites come from European countries or were developed by European researchers. These methodologies are often not applicable to the process of selection and managing geoheritage sites who fall outside of the usual cultural criteria or more broadly are located in the Global South.

Sayama talked about the need for explorations into the intersectionality of geoheritage, and the need for more educational and outreach programmes within existing sites. These could be ways to develop more **robust methodologies** for the selection and conservation of geoheritage sites.

They possess:

- ◆ Aesthetic dimension
- ◆ Dynamic dimension
- ◆ Varying scale
- ◆ Cultural connection

Margherita Colucci

talked about

How widespread diseases such as malaria are not exclusively linked to the Neolithic Revolution, but pre-date the advent of agriculture, and how they have driven changes in both demography and culture.

"We often ignore the role of diseases in the earliest periods of our species' prehistory."

Oscar Wilson

talked about

Ecometrics describes a trait-based approach used to understand variability in the environment through the relationship between **environmental variables** and **functional traits** within a community. Ecometric approaches can help us predict environments, both past and future, by focusing on the specific animal traits and what these can tell us about the environment. For example, stomata count in plants as a proxy for carbon dioxide concentration.

However, ecometrics are mostly studied in Euroasian and African animals, so the **current data does not quite apply to South America**. Wilson talked about to use body mass distributions in **South American herbivores** as a type of ecometric.

Damien Fordham

talked about

Woolly rhinoceros

At some point in the past, the climate changed in ways that **trapped** woolly rhinoceros populations in geographical pockets south of their optimal habitat. These populations found it **difficult to recolonise** and meet with other populations due to low dispersal rates, increasing snowfall, human hunting and other changes.

This is confirmed by a **multidisciplinary data approach**, using models that try to paint a picture of the past. The models are compared to paleo data and radio carbon dates to verify which model is closest in accuracy.

Celia Martin-Puertas

talked about

How **effective co-production** follows the three principles of **co-design, co-development and co-delivery** by involving stakeholders at **ALL** levels, from research planning, research itself, and outputs to be effective.

It may take a lot longer to do, but the end outputs of a co-developed project are **a lot more effective in reaching specific impact goals**, however defined.

Fumie Iizuka

talked about

"We are pursuing the topic of the peopling of the Americas during the final part of the last Ice Age from the northwestern Pacific Rim to North America."

Whereby using **archaeological evidence** - specifically the absence and presence pottery - new evidence is made available to test the hypothesis of how **humans migrated** from northeast Asia to North America by **coastal means**.

Ana Broström

talked about

The Core, an multidisciplinary project bringing together artists, poets, choreographers, musicians, geologists, a shaman, and a sediment core from **Lake Vomb** in Southern Sweden.

One of the artistic projects made watercolour paint to be used in a collective art piece and performance object. The pigments were developed from different temporal layers within the core:

 2000 years old

The art piece itself was an interaction between people and place. The final watercolour image a medium born from a **scientific project** hidden, out of sight, inaccessible in a way. For the art piece and materials themselves could not, in and of themselves, reveal their relationship to the scientific process.

Summer Praetorius

talked about

“By the time the ice-free corridor was open, populations in Siberia and North America were already genomically varying.”

TWO dominant theories suggest that **humans migrated** into North America either through the **Alaskan Coast** or through an **Ice-Free Corridor** formed between the Continental and Cordilleran Ice Sheets.

However, evidence of occupation at **sites south of the Ice-Free Corridor**, suggest that North America was **already well populated** before the Ice-Free Corridor formed.

Praetorius shared her research about how they have been **modelling freshwater input** from melting Ice-Sheets, which would have increased the strength of the Alaska currents. These currents flow northwards, making southwards human migration from Alaska into the rest of North America extremely difficult. This research could **help narrow down the timing** of when humans could have migrated into North America from Siberia via a coastal route with the technology that was available to them.

Aaron O'Dea

talked about

What happens when you take predators **OUT** of a coral reef?

"Over the last 7000 years predatory fishes like reef sharks have declined by 70%" And back then, humans were catching snappers that were bigger than those you can catch today."

With plenty of predators in a system, the numbers of prey are controlled, with knock-on effects down to the plankton.

But when predators are **removed**, say by human hunting, prey can become overpopulated. This can **change the way energy flows through the system.**

Bottom up

Top down

plankton = energy

For example,

Damsel fishes nibble on coral, to create a calcified “**chimney**” where algae grows. It is this Algae that the damsel fish feeds on.

7,000 years ago, damselfish populations were kept in check by plenty of predators. Now that the reefs have fewer predators, chimneys are an order of magnitude **more common today!**

Interconnected food webs often **respond unpredictably to small changes**, especially in complex ecosystems like coral reefs.

Understanding and predicting these responses is critical for appreciating life’s intricate fabric.

Michelle Kim

talked about

Wyoming’s particular geographic and cultural landscape presents an interesting area of study.

Citizens in Wyoming do **not like the term climate change**, but they agree that it is getting hotter and drier. Based on community focus data, they are most concerned with droughts they experienced in the past and the drought they will experience in the future at the family and economic level.

Combining quantitative data in the form of climate data analyses, and qualitative data in the form of community-based focus groups, it is possible to **use science communication to develop community adaptations.**

Paolo Albano

talked about

How the Mediterranean is already a collapsing ecosystem.

While the Mediterranean is a warm sea (20-31 °C in the summer), increased temperatures have led to native biodiversity collapse.

Native *Pinna nobilis* mass death due to pathogens.

Two things are reshaping the **Mediterranean** ecosystem. The collapse of native biodiversity on the one hand, and the direct connection between Mediterranean and the **Red Sea** through the **Suez Canal** on the other. The latter allowing invasive species to move into waters that are growing warmer and warmer.

Considering this effect is felt regionally and at different depths, maybe we **should focus conservation efforts** around those areas that act as **climate refugia for native biodiversity**.

Depth-related temperature differences

Miguel Matias

talked about

"How do you predict food web relationships through time?"

When people imagine a **lake environment**, they often are unaware that clues about how climate and surrounding areas have changed through time hide at the **bottom of the lake**. Pollen from plants, mineral run-off, and seasonal nutrient introduction from migratory animals, are deposited on the bottom of the lake, leaving an archive of changes over time.

By researching the histories of changes in the biospheres around lakes, researchers can identify the kinds of pressures that have affected the ecosystem, and, therefore, trophic relations.

James Scourse

talked about

"Doggerland conservation is like conserving a bombsite ecosystem."

Arctica islandica, a species of edible clam, has the [longest living](#) non-colonial metazoan species with an authenticated lifespan.

Their shells can provide a valuable resource for geochemical analyses for **understanding palaeoenvironmental change**. They are often dredged from the seafloor. We are also researching **middens** - piles of discarded domestic waste - usually from mollusc shells. Middens can provide **invaluable information** about human diet and behaviour in the past.

Caroline H Orr

talked about

"Soil is interesting!"

How different layers of archaeological context show different **microbial communities** associated with the context. **Begging the question:** is the microbial community contributing to the archaeological preservation, or are the archaeological remains allowing microbial community to exist in the first place?

At the **Vindolanda** archaeological site in Northumberland, England, microbes could be contributing to the preservation of Roman organic artefacts such as leather shoes.

Dr Orr's asks: If a changing climate changes the microbial communities, reducing preservation capacity, does it then inform archaeological efforts, approaches and timelines?

Tiffany Rivera

talked about

Using the **Wiki Commons** as a recipient platform for science communication projects. By sharing such projects under a **Creative Commons license**, researchers can simplify the process whereby **third parties** can use the project and make it their own.

Svetlana Radionovskaya

talked about

“If it fails to communicate the expected, or create the impact or action expected, has it [the outreach or science communication project] failed?”

Or is the intersection of art and science more about **exploring possibilities**?

How **conceptual art** – or art in which the ideas are more important than the execution or appearance – can be used within science communication projects as a way to **help audiences** visualise, understand and **interpret system complexity**. Whereby the abstraction inherent to conceptual art can help someone engage with a subject through an emotional and idea approach **before any textual thoughts** can get **in the way of the information**.

Gonzalo Oteo García

talked about

How, in the process of **creating science communication** outputs celebrating the 20-year excavation of 'The Giant of Segorbe', Oteo García and his collaborators developed a multidisciplinary editorial piece that also doubled as a novel research methodology.

A multidisciplinary project involving an **artistic**

recreation of the **Giant of Segorbe**, Oteo García and the artist [Vicent Gisbert Cardona](#) delved into the art history of the region. Choosing this approach opened up **new layers of data** that, combined with genomic sequencing from the *Giant of Segorbe's* remains and archaeological context, gave the researchers access to **new ways of visualising** how the *Giant of Segorbe* could have looked like when he was alive.

Hiroyuki Yamauchi

talked about

“Outreach and science communication can become research papers on their own.”

Gis

As little knowledge exists whether the application of **geographic information systems (GIS)** can improve the understanding high school students have of **disaster risk reduction**, Hiroyuki's team's project involved testing how well

students learned through either digital-only content, on-site content, and online-on-site mixed content. **The results showed:**

- 🌟 improved results on on-site implementations after utilising digital materials
- 🌟 less effectiveness of mixed online-on-site materials

Community outreach project like this provide specific value to the audience in question. But Hiroyuki's team went a step forward, **publishing the results as a scientific paper** of its own. This shows that outreach projects can, in and of themselves, provide researchers with further publication opportunities.

This shows the multiple avenues of value generation outreach projects can have, and helps us imagine method in which an **outreach project** provides not just **community and audience value**, but **professional value** in the form of opening alternative **publication routes in different or tangential fields.**

Elodie Brisset

talked about

An Action vs. laissez-faire approach in the protection of peatland environments.

"How to ensure restoration of peatlands will last?"

Erin Dillon

talked about

"How the Caribbean used to be so much more *sharky* than today"

Should we invite Dave to hang with?

Nah. It will get too crowded otherwise.

How many sharks should there be on coral reefs in the absence of human disturbance? We can shed light on this question by figuring out what the baseline of shark populations is, something Dillon finds out by identifying which **types of sharks** were most common and when using **shark scales (dermal denticles) in the fossil record**

In the Caribbean, shark populations have declined severely. But in the Pacific, decline rates is lower, in parts thanks to the **seasonal upwelling of nutrient rich water**.

Michael-Shawn Fletcher

talked about

The **natural environment** is bound by **cultural perception**. As such, there exists a dogma whereby society, researchers, policy-makers, etc. only **identify human-made** change where the current environments diverge from this **cultural perception** of what should be a **natural environment**.

"The country needs care."

Fletcher described the example of the **changing landscapes** of Australia.

60,000 ya
Years Ago

60,000 ya
Fire-based
managed landscape

10,000 ya
New Landscape

British
Invasion

Eukalyptus
Plantations

2020 Wildfires

Before humans first migrated to what is now called Australia, there existed a **natural environment**. Humans changed this environment with practices such as controlled burning. This, over ten thousand years, became a **new kind of natural landscape** as humans became part and actively modified it. When the **British invaded**, this changes yet again, and eventually a landscape of **eukalyptus plantations** is seen as **common and natural**. Eukalyptus is an extremely flammable tree, which compounded the wildfires seen in 2020.

Leading to the question of what will be Australia's **future "natural landscape"**?

"We need to accept our responsibility to care for the world."

These were some of the talks I attended during INQUA. Of which there were hundreds, as well as hundreds of fascinating research posters. My experience, as a lay person and science communicator, of INQUA was a truly enriching one. Concepts I had never heard of summarised in this report: cultural landscape, GIS, geoheritage, and more have **enriched my understanding of the human-made and the “natural” worlds** – the division of which is much thinner than I ever, tacitly, imagined!

Myself and my team at Cooked Illustrations have created this report, late as it may be to publication, as a way to share some of this knowledge more broadly. The **information created and shared by researchers** at conferences deserves and **needs to be available in formats that lay people, regular audiences, can engage with and contribute to.**

It is our mission at Cooked Illustrations to help in this regard.

If you have found this document of value, consider contacting the researchers by clicking on the links here, sharing it to colleagues and friends, or telling the world about the work Cooked Illustrations does.

We can only continue to do this through your support.

ian cooke-tapia
Panama, 2025

The conference ended with a show by the amazing music ensemble [EtnoMuSa](#), “an orchestra and music laboratory for traditional folk music”, a musical project from the Sapienza **Universita di Roma**, the host of the conference.

More conferences should platform local artistic acts.

**See you next
time at...**

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